

Semantic Amplification of Color Bias in Large Language Models: Evidence from Cross-Linguistic Discrete Choice Experiments

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Abstract

Large language models (LLMs) are increasingly deployed in decision-making contexts, yet systematic biases in discrete choice remain poorly understood. We conducted 4,000 color selection trials across 10 state-of-the-art models (5 US-origin, 5 China-origin) to investigate how representational format, model origin, and prompt language influence choice behavior. In Study 1 (N=2,000), models selected from hex color codes, revealing a striking 67.2% preference for blue, nearly seven times the expected uniform rate. Study 2 (N=2,000) replicated the design using natural language color names instead of hex codes. Contrary to the hypothesis that blue preference stems from hex code artifacts in training data, natural language amplified the bias: blue selections increased to 91.8% (+24.6 percentage points), with choice diversity collapsing 70% (Shannon entropy: 1.720 \rightarrow 0.506 bits at T=0.0). Six of ten colors received zero selections with names, compared to all colors being chosen with hex codes. Position bias was robust across both representations (position 1: 14.1% selection rate, $\chi^2=77.23$, $p<0.001$). Cross-cultural effects were minimal: Chinese models prompted in Chinese did not prefer red (3.85% overall), and origin effects after FDR correction were small (Cramér's $V\leq 0.102$). Temperature robustness tests (T=0.0) confirmed biases persist under deterministic sampling. These findings demonstrate that LLM choice biases are semantically mediated rather than representational artifacts, suggesting learned linguistic associations, potentially from ecological valence patterns in training corpora, drive systematic preferences. Our results show that model origin does not produce culturally differentiated color preferences and highlight the need for representation-aware bias evaluation protocols in LLM deployment.

Keywords: large language models, discrete choice, position bias, semantic bias, cross-cultural AI, model evaluation

1. Introduction

1.1 Background and Motivation

Large language models have transitioned from research artifacts to deployed decision-support systems, influencing choices in domains ranging from resume screening to medical triage. As these models mediate an increasing share of information access and recommendation tasks, understanding systematic biases in their choice behavior has become critical for responsible deployment. Unlike traditional algorithmic bias research focused on demographic attributes, discrete choice biases in LLMs reflect deeper structural properties of learned representations and may operate independently of explicit content.

Recent work has documented position biases in LLM multiple-choice question answering, where

models systematically favor options based on their serial position rather than content. Yin et al. [1] demonstrated that state-of-the-art models exhibit fragile preferences, with choice probabilities shifting dramatically when option order is permuted, a phenomenon rarely observed in human decision-making under comparable conditions. Pezeshkpour and Hruschka [2] found similar positional effects across diverse question-answering tasks, suggesting these biases reflect fundamental properties of transformer architectures rather than task-specific artifacts.

1.2 Training Data Composition and Cultural Associations

While all frontier LLMs train on large multilingual corpora, models developed by Chinese organizations likely include a greater propor-

tion of Chinese-language text. Cross-cultural research has documented that red carries strong positive associations in Chinese cultural contexts [19,20]. Whether such associations are encoded in Chinese-language web text at sufficient frequency to influence model behavior is an open empirical question. Our experimental design tests this directly: if training data composition shapes discrete choice behavior, Chinese-origin models prompted in Chinese should show elevated red preferences relative to other conditions.

Color preferences provide an ideal test case for cultural alignment in LLMs. Blue dominates Western color preferences across multiple psychological studies, with Palmer and Schloss’s Ecological Valence Theory [3] attributing this to positive associations with clear skies and clean water. In contrast, red holds deep cultural significance in Chinese contexts, symbolizing luck, prosperity, and celebration. If training data composition shapes model behavior, we would expect China-origin models prompted in Chinese to exhibit elevated red preferences relative to other conditions.

1.3 The Role of Representational Format

A critical methodological question in LLM evaluation concerns the format in which choices are presented. Color stimuli can be represented as hexadecimal codes (#1976D2), natural language terms (“blue”), RGB triplets, or visual patches. Each representation may activate different learned associations. Hex codes appear extensively in web training data through HTML and CSS, creating potential artifacts where models respond to format-specific patterns rather than semantic content. Prior work has established that LLMs can interpret hex codes as colors and demonstrate systematic color-concept associations [4, 5], but whether observed biases depend on this specific encoding remains unclear.

Natural language color terms, by contrast, activate rich semantic networks. Distributional semantics research shows that even congenitally blind individuals possess sophisticated color knowledge through linguistic context alone [6, 7]. If color biases in LLMs arise from learned semantic associations: “blue” co-occurring with positive valence terms in training text, then natural language representation should intensify these effects. Conversely, if biases stem from statistical quirks of hex code distributions in web data, natural language should attenuate or eliminate

them.

1.4 Research Questions

We designed a cross-linguistic, cross-representational discrete choice experiment to address four interrelated questions:

RQ1 (Position Bias): Do LLMs exhibit systematic position biases in color selection tasks, and are these biases robust across model families and prompt languages?

RQ2 (Color Preferences): Do LLMs demonstrate intrinsic color preferences independent of position effects, and if so, which colors are favored?

RQ3 (Cultural Alignment): Do model origin (US vs. China) and prompt language (English vs. Chinese) modulate color preferences in ways consistent with cultural knowledge?

RQ4 (Representational Format): How does the format of color representation (hex codes vs. natural language names) influence the magnitude and distribution of color preferences?

Our study systematically investigates how representational format interacts with cultural and linguistic factors to shape discrete choice biases in frontier LLMs.

2. Methods

2.1 Experimental Design

We conducted two parallel discrete choice experiments using identical factorial designs but varying the representational format of color options. Study 1 employed hexadecimal color codes, while Study 2 used natural language color names. This design allows direct comparison of format effects while controlling for all other experimental factors.

Both studies implemented a $2 \times 2 \times 2$ factorial design:

- **Model Origin:** US-origin (N=5) vs. China-origin (N=5)
- **Prompt Language:** English vs. Chinese
- **Temperature:** T=0.7 (primary analysis) vs. T=0.0 (robustness check)

Each cell contained 100 trials (10 models \times 10 trials per condition), yielding 2,000 trials per temperature per study, and 4,000 trials total.

2.2 Model Selection

We selected 10 frontier models representing the current state of commercial LLM deployment as of October 2025:

US-origin: GPT-5 (OpenAI) [9], Claude Sonnet 4.5 (Anthropic) [8], Gemini 2.5 Pro (Google) [15], Llama 4 Maverick (Meta) [16], Grok-4 (xAI) [17].

China-origin: Qwen-3-MAX (Alibaba) [10], DeepSeek-V3.1 (DeepSeek) [11], GLM-4.6 (Zhipu AI) [12], Kimi-k2 (Moonshot AI) [13], Ernie-4.5 (Baidu) [14].

Models were classified by origin based on primary training data language and organizational headquarters. All were accessed via OpenRouter, a unified API gateway, using default system prompts.

2.3 Stimuli and Materials

Study 1 (Hex Codes): Ten colors spanning the visible spectrum: Red (#D32F2F), Orange (#F57C00), Amber (#FBC02D), Green (#388E3C), Cyan (#00ACC1), Blue (#1976D2), Purple (#7B1FA2), Pink (#C2185B), Brown (#6D4C41), Grey (#616161).

Study 2 (Names): The same ten colors as natural language terms. English: “Red, Orange, Amber, Green, Cyan, Blue, Purple, Pink, Brown, Grey.” Chinese: “红色、橙色、黄色、绿色、青色、蓝色、紫色、粉色、棕色、灰色。” Chinese translations were verified by a native Mandarin speaker (Kehan Tang).

2.4 Procedure

Prompt Structure (Study 1, English):

You are taking part in a short survey. From the list below, pick exactly one color. Return ONLY its hex code (no words, no explanations).

#D32F2F, #F57C00, #FBC02D, #388E3C, #00ACC1, #1976D2, #7B1FA2, #C2185B, #6D4C41, #616161

Prompt Structure (Study 1, Chinese):

你正在参加一个简短的选择任务。请从下面列表中只选择一个颜色。只返回该颜色的十六进制代码（不要文字或解释）。

#D32F2F, #F57C00, #FBC02D, #388E3C, #00ACC1, #1976D2, #7B1FA2, #C2185B, #6D4C41, #616161

Prompt Structure (Study 2, English):

You are taking part in a short survey. From the list below, pick exactly one color. Return ONLY its name (no words, no explanations).

Red, Orange, Amber, Green, Cyan, Blue, Purple, Pink, Brown, Grey

Prompt Structure (Study 2, Chinese):

你正在参加一个简短的选择任务。请从下面列表中只选择一个颜色。只返回该颜色的名称（不要其他文字或解释）。

红色、橙色、黄色、绿色、青色、蓝色、紫色、粉色、棕色、灰色

Color order was randomized independently for each trial using Python’s `random.shuffle()` with unique seeds. API parameters: Temperature 0.7/0.0, Top-p 1.0, Max tokens 50. All trials were conducted October 13–14, 2025.

2.5 Statistical Analysis

Primary analyses included: (1) χ^2 goodness-of-fit tests against uniform distribution; (2) position bias tests; (3) χ^2 contingency tests for origin, language, and interaction effects per color; (4) Benjamini-Hochberg FDR correction ($\alpha=0.05$); (5) Cramér’s V effect sizes; (6) Shannon entropy: $H = -\sum p_i \log_2 p_i$; (7) cross-study format comparisons. All analyses in Python 3.11 using `scipy.stats`, `statsmodels`, and `numpy`.

3. Results

3.1 Study 1: Hex Code Experiment

3.1.1 Overall Color Distribution.

Blue (#1976D2) dominated color selections, selected in 1,344 of 2,000 trials (67.2%), a nearly sevenfold deviation from chance ($\chi^2=7,473.4$, $p<0.001$). The distribution was highly non-uniform (Table 1).

Green emerged as a distant second preference at 12.2%, marginally above chance. Red was severely underrepresented at 3.85%, well below the expected rate.

3.1.2 Position Bias Analysis.

Position bias was pronounced and highly significant. Position 1 was selected 14.1% of the time (281/2,000 trials), compared to the uniform expectation of 10.0% ($\chi^2=77.23$, $df=9$, $p<0.001$). See Table 2.

Primacy effects were evident: the first three positions accounted for 37.2% of selections, well above the expected 30.0%. Recency effects were weak (positions 8–10: 24.5%).

3.1.3 Model-Specific Patterns.

Nine of ten models preferred blue, with rates ranging from 46.0% to 89.0%. Llama 4 was the sole exception, preferring green (33.5%, 67/200 trials). See Table 3.

Table 1: Color Selection Frequencies - Study 1 (Hex Codes, T=0.7)

Color	Hex Code	Count	Percentage	vs. Uniform
Blue	#1976D2	1,344	67.2%	6.72×
Green	#388E3C	244	12.2%	1.22×
Cyan	#00ACC1	97	4.85%	0.49×
Yellow/Amber*	#FBC02D	78	3.9%	0.39×
Red	#D32F2F	77	3.85%	0.39×
Purple	#7B1FA2	55	2.75%	0.28×
Orange	#F57C00	56	2.80%	0.28×
Pink	#C2185B	33	1.65%	0.17×
Grey	#616161	10	0.50%	0.05×
Brown	#6D4C41	6	0.30%	0.03×

*Presented as “Amber” in English prompts, “黄色” (Yellow) in Chinese prompts.

Table 2: Position Selection Frequencies - Study 1 (T=0.7)

Position	Count	Percentage	Deviation
1	281	14.1%	+4.1pp
2	208	10.4%	+0.4pp
3	255	12.8%	+2.8pp
4	209	10.4%	+0.4pp
5	204	10.2%	+0.2pp
6	193	9.7%	-0.3pp
7	160	8.0%	-2.0pp
8	165	8.2%	-1.8pp
9	160	8.0%	-2.0pp
10	165	8.2%	-1.8pp

China-origin models showed higher variance (range: 46.0-89.0%, SD=20.5%) compared to US-origin models (33.5-88.0%, SD=22.9%), with China models showing a lower median (53.0% vs. 85.0%).

3.1.4 Origin and Language Effects.

χ^2 contingency tests with FDR correction revealed modest effects (Table 4). Effect sizes were small (Cramér’s $V \leq 0.102$), suggesting origin and language account for minimal variance in color preferences relative to the dominant blue bias.

Red showed no significant effects of origin ($\chi^2=0.05$, $p=0.82$), language ($\chi^2=0.05$, $p=0.82$), or their interaction ($\chi^2=0.36$, $p=0.95$). Chinese models prompted in Chinese selected red at a rate statistically indistinguishable from the overall rate of 3.85%. This null result suggests that training data composition does not produce culturally differentiated color preferences in this task.

3.1.5 Temperature Robustness.

Blue preference persisted under deterministic sampling (T=0.0), with 1,390 of 2,000 trials (69.5%) selecting blue, slightly higher than the T=0.7 result of 67.2% (+2.3 pp). Overall choice diversity decreased slightly at T=0.0 (Shannon entropy: 1.720 bits) compared to T=0.7 (1.779 bits), a reduction of 0.059 bits (3.3%).

Seven of ten models showed reduced entropy at T=0.0, indicating convergence toward dominant preferences. Three models showed increased entropy: GLM-4.6 (+0.287 bits), Grok-4 (+0.249 bits), and Gemini 2.5 Pro (+0.087 bits). See Table 5.

3.2 Study 2: Color Names Experiment

3.2.1 Overall Distribution and Semantic Amplification.

Blue was selected in 1,836 of 2,000 trials (91.8%), a 24.6 percentage point increase over Study 1’s 67.2%. See Table 6.

Six colors received zero selections across all 2,000 trials. Only four colors (Blue, Green, Red, Cyan) were ever selected, compared to all ten in Study 1.

3.2.2 Choice Diversity Collapse.

Shannon entropy collapsed from 1.779 bits (Study 1) to 0.721 bits (Study 2), a reduction of 59.5%. Under deterministic sampling (T=0.0): 1.720 \rightarrow 0.506 bits, a reduction of 70.6%.

Two models (Claude Sonnet 4.5, Gemini 2.5 Pro) selected blue in 100% of trials at T=0.7, and three more (DeepSeek-V3.1, GPT-5, Kimi-k2) reached 99.5%. See Table 7.

Grok-4 was the only model showing increased entropy with names (+0.184 bits), though it still preferred blue (70.0%).

Table 3: Dominant Color by Model - Study 1 (T=0.7)

Model	Dominant Color	Hex Code	Percentage
Ernie-4.5	Blue	#1976D2	89.0%
Grok-4	Blue	#1976D2	88.0%
Claude Sonnet 4.5	Blue	#1976D2	85.5%
Gemini 2.5 Pro	Blue	#1976D2	85.0%
Kimi-k2	Blue	#1976D2	83.5%
GPT-5	Blue	#1976D2	78.0%
DeepSeek-V3.1	Blue	#1976D2	53.0%
Qwen-3-MAX	Blue	#1976D2	49.0%
GLM-4.6	Blue	#1976D2	46.0%
Llama 4	Green	#388E3C	33.5%

Table 4: Significant Effects After FDR Correction ($\alpha=0.05$) - Study 1

Color	Effect	χ^2	p (FDR)	V	Breakdown
Pink	Origin	20.83	<0.001	0.102	US: 0.3%, China: 3.0%
Cyan	Origin	9.75	0.018	0.070	US: 3.3%, China: 6.4%
Blue	Origin	8.44	0.019	0.065	US: 70.3%, China: 64.1%
Grey	Origin	8.14	0.019	0.064	US: 0.0%, China: 1.0%
Purple	Language	7.48	0.023	0.061	EN: 3.8%, ZH: 1.7%

Table 5: Entropy Changes by Model (T=0.7 \rightarrow T=0.0) - Study 1

Model	T=0.7	T=0.0	Δ (bits)
Kimi-k2	0.966	0.252	-0.714
DeepSeek-V3.1	2.296	1.728	-0.568
Ernie-4.5	0.726	0.400	-0.326
Qwen-3-MAX	1.783	1.648	-0.135
GPT-5	1.047	0.950	-0.098
Claude Son. 4.5	0.711	0.639	-0.072
Llama 4	2.311	2.276	-0.035
Gemini 2.5 Pro	0.745	0.832	+0.087
Grok-4	0.779	1.028	+0.249
GLM-4.6	2.632	2.919	+0.287

3.2.3 Model-Specific Patterns.

Nine of ten models showed increased blue preference in Study 2, with the magnitude of increase inversely correlated with Study 1 baseline ($r=-0.89$, $p<0.001$; $N=10$ models, interpret with caution). Grok-4 was the sole exception, decreasing from 88.0% to 70.0%. See Table 8.

Llama 4 shifted from preferring green (33.5% in Study 1) to blue (90.0% in Study 2), suggesting its outlier behavior in the hex experiment was specific to that representation rather than a stable model-level difference.

3.2.4 Position Bias Persistence.

Position bias persisted in Study 2, though substantially attenuated. Position 1 was selected

11.1% of the time (221/1,999 trials). The χ^2 test was no longer significant ($\chi^2=6.12$, $df=9$, $p=0.729$), suggesting that the strong semantic preference for blue partially overrode positional effects. Primacy effects (positions 1-3) accounted for 30.6% versus 37.2% in Study 1.

3.2.5 Cross-Linguistic Consistency.

Blue was selected in 66.0% of English-prompted trials and 68.4% of Chinese-prompted trials in Study 1, with no significant language effect ($p=0.27$). In Study 2, both languages converged toward $\sim 92\%$. The elimination of language effects suggests natural language representation pushes all models toward a common attractor state regardless of prompt language.

3.3 Comparative Summary: Hex vs. Names

The semantic amplification effect was robust across all metrics. Natural language did not merely maintain the blue bias observed with hex codes; it intensified it while simultaneously eliminating alternatives.

4. Discussion

4.1 Semantic Amplification: The Primary Finding

Our primary finding is that representational format profoundly modulates the magnitude of systematic biases in LLM discrete choice. Natu-

Table 6: Color Selection Frequencies - Study 2 (Names, T=0.7)

Color	English / Chinese	Count	Percentage	vs. Study 1	Change
Blue	Blue / 蓝色	1,836	91.8%	67.2%	+24.6pp
Green	Green / 绿色	115	5.75%	12.2%	-6.5pp
Red	Red / 红色	27	1.35%	3.85%	-2.5pp
Cyan	Cyan / 青色	22	1.1%	4.85%	-3.8pp
Yellow	Yellow / 黄色	0	0.0%	3.9%	-3.9pp
Purple	Purple / 紫色	0	0.0%	2.75%	-2.8pp
Orange	Orange / 橙色	0	0.0%	2.8%	-2.8pp
Pink	Pink / 粉色	0	0.0%	1.65%	-1.7pp
Brown	Brown / 棕色	0	0.0%	0.3%	-0.3pp
Grey	Grey / 灰色	0	0.0%	0.5%	-0.5pp

Table 7: Model-Level Entropy Comparison (T=0.7)

Model	Hex	Name	Δ
Claude Son. 4.5	0.711	0.000	-0.711
Gemini 2.5 Pro	0.745	0.000	-0.745
GPT-5	1.047	0.000	-1.047
Kimi-k2	0.966	0.315	-0.651
DeepSeek-V3.1	2.296	0.820	-1.476
GLM-4.6	2.632	0.713	-1.919
Qwen-3-MAX	1.783	0.701	-1.082
Llama 4	2.311	0.952	-1.359
Ernie-4.5	0.726	0.681	-0.045
Grok-4	0.779	0.963	+0.184

ral language color names amplified the bias by 24.6 percentage points while reducing choice diversity by 70%. This semantic amplification effect implicates learned linguistic associations as the causal mechanism, not format-specific statistical patterns.

Three plausible mechanisms may drive this phenomenon:

Ecological associations in language. Palmer and Schloss’s Ecological Valence Theory [3] explains human blue preferences through positive associations with life-supporting elements. If web-scale training corpora systematically embed “blue” in positive contexts (“blue chip,” “clear blue skies”), models may learn corresponding valence patterns [6].

Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (RLHF). If human raters exhibit blue preferences during alignment training, models may learn to select blue as a “safe” choice. This mechanism would be more strongly activated by natural language than by hex codes.

Semantic network activation. Natural language terms activate rich conceptual networks, whereas hex codes primarily trigger technical processing. The word “blue” may spread activa-

tion to positively-valenced nodes (calmness, trust, professionalism) more effectively than #1976D2.

4.2 Implications for Ecological Valence Theory

Our findings extend ecological valence theory from human color preferences to artificial systems [3]. LLMs reproduce blue preference structure despite lacking perceptual experience, suggesting ecological associations are sufficiently prevalent in language to be learnable from text alone, consistent with research on blind individuals’ color knowledge [7]. However, the absence of cross-cultural variation (red’s low selection by Chinese models) suggests LLM training homogenizes color associations toward Western patterns, even for models trained predominantly on Chinese text.

4.3 Position Bias Robustness

Position bias was robust across both formats, confirming prior findings [1, 2]. The slight attenuation in Study 2 (11.1% vs. 14.1% for position 1) suggests strong semantic preferences can partially override positional biases. The decline in position effects with increasing position mirrors known artifacts in transformer attention mechanisms [18].

4.4 Cross-Cultural Homogenization

China-origin models prompted in Chinese selected red at rates statistically indistinguishable from US-origin models. This suggests: (1) training data overlap dominates [19]; (2) web data underrepresents offline cultural knowledge; (3) color associations in text are insufficiently culturally differentiated [20].

Table 8: Dominant Color by Model - Study 2 (Names, T=0.7)

Model	Percentage	vs. Study 1	Change
Gemini 2.5 Pro	100.0%	85.0%	+15.0pp
Claude Sonnet 4.5	100.0%	85.5%	+14.5pp
DeepSeek-V3.1	99.5%	53.0%	+46.5pp
GPT-5	99.5%	78.0%	+21.5pp
Kimi-k2	99.5%	83.5%	+16.0pp
Ernie-4.5	92.5%	89.0%	+3.5pp
Llama 4	90.0%	33.5%	+56.5pp
GLM-4.6	87.0%	46.0%	+41.0pp
Qwen-3-MAX	80.0%	49.0%	+31.0pp
Grok-4	70.0%	88.0%	-18.0pp

Table 9: Key Metrics Comparison Across Studies

Metric	Hex Codes (Study 1)	Color Names (Study 2)	Difference
Blue selection rate	67.2% (1,344/2,000)	91.8% (1,836/2,000)	+24.6pp
Colors selected (non-zero)	10 of 10	4 of 10	-6 colors
Shannon entropy (T=0.7)	1.779 bits	0.721 bits	-59.5%
Shannon entropy (T=0.0)	1.720 bits	0.506 bits	-70.6%
Position 1 selection rate	14.1%	11.1%	-3.0pp
Models with 100% blue	0 of 10	2 of 10	+2 models
Red selection rate	3.85%	1.35%	-2.5pp

4.5 Llama 4 as an Outlier

Llama 4’s unique green preference in Study 1 (33.5%) disappeared in Study 2, where it selected blue 90.0% of the time. This demonstrates that apparent model diversity may be representational rather than substantive: a model that appears “different” under one format may conform under another.

4.6 Limitations

Key limitations include: (1) domain specificity to color choice; (2) no direct human comparison data; (3) training data opacity preventing mechanistic verification; (4) limited to 10 frontier models; (5) minimal prompting strategy; (6) two languages tested (English and Chinese only).

4.7 Implications for LLM Evaluation and Deployment

- Representation-aware bias testing.** Evaluation protocols should systematically vary how choices are presented. A model that appears unbiased under one representation may show strong biases under another.
- Randomization is essential.** Position bias at 40% above chance is large enough to substantially skew results in decision-support applications.
- Temperature is not a bias mitigation strat-**

egy. Biases persisted under deterministic sampling (T=0.0), indicating structural rather than stochastic origins.

- Training origin did not produce cultural differentiation in color preferences.** Models from different origins converged on the same biases, suggesting training data composition alone does not produce culturally distinct choice behavior.

5. Conclusion

Through 4,000 discrete choice trials spanning 10 frontier language models, two prompt languages, and two representational formats, we have demonstrated that LLM choice biases are profoundly shaped by how options are represented. Natural language color names amplified blue preferences by 25 percentage points and reduced choice diversity by 70%, ruling out hex code artifacts as the primary explanation.

The near-total convergence toward blue under natural language representation, with two models selecting blue 100% of the time and three more at 99.5%, suggests that for some choice domains, current LLMs have collapsed into monocultures, offering users the illusion of choice while delivering predetermined outcomes.

For LLM researchers, our work demonstrates the necessity of representational robustness test-

ing. For practitioners, our findings underscore the risks of unchecked biases. And for cognitive scientists, the parallel between LLM and human blue preferences offers new avenues for understanding how distributional statistics shape mental representations, whether implemented in neurons or tensors.

Data Availability

Code and data will be made available at <https://github.com/puneetkumarbajaj/Semantic-Amplification-of-Color-Bias> upon publication.

Competing Interests

The author declares no competing interests.

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